

Second Dissociation Constant of Succinic Acid from 0° to 50° by e.m.f. Method Based on Modified Davies Equation

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The second thermodynamic dissociation constant, K_2 , of succinic acid from 0° to 50° at an interval of 5 degrees were recalculated from the experimental data of electromotive forces measured by Pinching and Bates on the basis of modified Davies equation. The recalculated values of pK_2 differ by 2 to 3 in the second place of decimal at each temperature.

PINCHING and Bates¹ measured the e.m.f. of the cell,

to determine the second thermodynamic dissociation constant, K_2 of succinic acid (H_2Suc) from 0° to 50° at 5 degrees interval. In computation of the actual concentrations of the succinate and bisuccinate ions, they assumed $f_{H^+}f_{HSuc^-}$ to be equal to $f_{H^+}f_{Cl^-}$ and used

$$-\log f_{H^+}f_{Cl^-} = \frac{2A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + Ba \sqrt{\mu}}$$

with $a=7$ by trial for hydrogen ion correction. They used notation 'f' for activity coefficient, though computation of concentrations were made in molality scale. For the first dissociation constant, K_1 correction over K_2 of succinic acid, they used the method described elsewhere².

Results and Discussion

Since K_1/K_2 is about 25 for succinic acid, K_1 has to be taken into account in the calculation of K_2 . However, even an error of ± 0.05 in pK_1 does not make any appreciable change in pK_2 because the amount of H_2Suc formed is small. An approximate value of pK_1 with an uncertainty of ± 0.025 were recalculated from the e.m.f. values³ of the cell (C-2),

using modified Davies equation⁴ for the computation of activity coefficients. Thus, e.m.f. of both the cells (C-1) and (C-2) are given by

$$m_{H^+} = \text{antilog} \left[\frac{(E^\circ - E)F}{2.30259RT} + \frac{2A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \beta\mu - \log m_{Cl^-} \right] \dots (1)$$

For the cells (C-1) and (C-2), β will remain same as in cell (C-3) irrespective of the composition of ion atmosphere⁴⁻⁶.

Assuming complete suppression of the bisuccinate ion dissociation due to presence of fairly high hydrogen ion concentration in the cell (C-2),

$$m_{H_2Suc} = m - m_{H^+} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$m_{HSuc^-} = 1.5 m - m_{H_2Suc} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$\text{and, } \mu = 1.5 m + m_{H^+} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

With the help of equations (1), (2), (3) and (4) and using the method of successive approximation, values for each m_{H^+} , m_{HSuc^-} , m_{H_2Suc} and μ were calculated up to 6th place of decimal. In equation (1), values for E° were taken from Harned and Ehlers⁷, β from Sinha, Ghosh and Prasad⁶ and E from Pinching and Bates⁸.

The first dissociation equilibrium of succinic acid can be represented by equation(5),

$$\log \frac{m_{H^+}m_{HSuc^-}}{m_{H_2Suc}} - \frac{2A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_1 - \beta_1 \mu \dots (5)$$

Values for $\log K_1$ and β_1 were found out from the intercepts and slopes of the rough straight lines obtained from the plot of L.H.S. against μ . In Table 1, these rough values of $\log K_1$ and β_1 have been recorded.

From the consideration of electrical neutrality for solutions of cell (C-1),

$$m_{Na^+} + m_{H^+} = m_{HSuc^-} + 2m_{Suc^{2-}} + m_{Cl^-}$$

$$\text{or, } 7m + m_{H^+} = m_{HSuc^-} + 2m_{Suc^{2-}} \dots (6)$$

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TABLE 1—(APPROXIMATE) VALUES OF $\log K_1$ AND β_1

Temp. (°C)	$-\log K_1$	β_1
0	4.258	0.363
5	4.237	0.388
10	4.219	0.330
15	4.205	0.342
20	4.192	0.360
25	4.183	0.360
30	4.174	0.353
35	4.169	0.336
40	4.166	0.342
45	4.165	0.348
50	4.164	0.332

Total succinate entities present in the same cell is given by,

$$4m = m_{\text{Suc}^-} + m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}} \quad \dots (7)$$

Multiplication of equation (7) by 2, and subtracting equation (6) from it, then results

$$m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 2m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}} = (m - m_{\text{H}^+}) \quad \dots (8)$$

Now, the ionic strength,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= \frac{1}{2}(m_{\text{Na}^+} + m_{\text{Cl}^-}) + \frac{1}{2}m_{\text{H}^+} + \frac{1}{2}m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 2m_{\text{Suc}^-} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}m + \frac{1}{2}(m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 2m_{\text{Suc}^-} - 7m) + \frac{1}{2}m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 2m_{\text{Suc}^-} \\ &= 3m + m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 3m_{\text{Suc}^-} \quad \dots (9) \end{aligned}$$

because from equation (6),

$$m_{\text{H}^+} = m_{\text{HSuc}^-} + 2m_{\text{Suc}^-} - 7m$$

An arbitrary value to μ was assigned in equation (1) and the corresponding value of m_{H^+} was calculated. For this purpose E° from Harned and Ehlers⁷ and β from Sinha, Ghosh and Prasad⁸ were taken as before. Electromotive forces, E of cell (C-1) were taken from Pinching and Bates¹. The value of m_{H^+} so obtained was fed in equations (5) and (8), and the corresponding values for m_{HSuc^-} and $m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}}$ were calculated. Values of m_{Suc^-} was found out from equation (7). From these values of m_{HSuc^-} and m_{Suc^-} , a fresh value for μ was calculated with the help of equation (9). This fresh value of μ was again fed into equation (1) and the corresponding values of m_{H^+} and hence m_{HSuc^-} , m_{Suc^-} and $m_{\text{H}_2\text{Suc}}$ were calculated. This iteration process was repeated till their constant values up to 6th. place of decimal were obtained.

The equilibrium of acid succinate ion, i.e.,

can be represented by,

$$\log \frac{m_{\text{H}^+} m_{\text{Suc}^-}}{m_{\text{HSuc}^-}} - \frac{4A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_2 - \beta_2 \mu \quad \dots (10)$$

A plot of L.H.S. of equation (10) against μ was found to be a perfect straight line. The recalculations were confined up to $\mu \leq 0.2$, up to which modified Davies equation holds good in this case. Plots

at 5°, 25° and 50° have been shown in Figure 1. Plots at other temperatures are similar. Values for $\log K_2$ and β_2 were found out from the intercepts and slopes of the plots. The values of $\log K_2$ and β_2 have been recorded in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Plots of L.H.S. against μ at 5°, 25° & 50°C

TABLE 2

Temp. (°C)	$-\log K_2$		β_2
	Bates value	Recal. value	
0	5.674	5.695	0.836
5	5.661	5.680	0.817
10	5.649	5.671	0.794
15	5.643	5.664	0.806
20	5.639	5.661	0.816
25	5.636	5.658	0.836
30	5.642	5.663	0.819
35	5.648	5.670	0.804
40	5.654	5.680	0.799
45	5.670	5.692	0.798
50	5.680	5.699	0.828

Recalculated values of K_2 were found to fit well in equation,

$$pK_2 = 1679.13/T - 5.6824 + 0.019153T \quad \dots (11)$$

over the temperature range from 0° to 50°.

Thermodynamic Functions :

The recalculated values of $\log K_2$ and those reported by Pinching and Bates¹ differ by about 0.02

at each temperature, i.e., about 0.4%. Hence, recalculation of other thermodynamic quantities are not necessary.

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